

This is the set of quantum weirdness, which goes as followed:

- The particle set place, 0th weirdness paired 0th weirdness, the extra 0th weirdness, which make the outcome of another 0th weirdness.
- The orb set place, 1st weirdness paired 1st weirdness, the extra 1st weirdness, which make the outcome of another 1st weirdness.
- The string set place, 2nd weirdness paired 2nd weirdness, the extra 2nd weirdness, which make the outcome of another 2nd weirdness.
- The wave set place, 3rd weirdness paired 3rd weirdness, the extra 3rd weirdness, which make the outcome of another 3rd weirdness.
- The field set place, 4th weirdness paired 4th weirdness, the extra 4th weirdness, which make the outcome of another 4th weirdness.
- The fluctuations set place, 5th weirdness paired 5th weirdness, the extra 5th weirdness, which make the outcome of another 5th weirdness.

Set.